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Exploring Students' Perceptions of the English for General Communication Class and Its Impact on Speaking Skills

Diah Rini Melati, Dameria Sidabalok

Universitas Bandar Lampung

Email: d.rini2601@gmail.com

Abstract

The study investigates student perceptions of English for General Communication classes in enhancing their English-speaking skills at the English Language Laboratory, Bandar Lampung University, during the odd semester of 2023/2024. This quantitative descriptive research employed a survey method, utilizing questionnaires for data collection and descriptive statistical analysis through percentages. The study population consisted of 345 students enrolled in the English for General Communication classes, with a randomly selected sample of 284 students (10% of the total). The findings reveal that student perceptions of the course were largely positive, with 2.5% (7 students) rating it as very positive, 49.3% (140 students) as positive, 24.3% (69 students) as moderate, 10.9% (31 students) as negative, and 13.0% (37 students) as very negative. Overall, the results indicate that the majority of students perceive the English for General Communication classes as beneficial for developing their speaking skills, categorizing their perceptions within the positive range. These findings suggest that the course plays a significant role in enhancing students' English-speaking abilities, highlighting the effectiveness of the teaching methods and learning environment provided at the English Language Laboratory. The study underscores the importance of continuously improving instructional strategies and resources to further support students in their language acquisition journey.

Keywords : *Student Perception, English for General Communication, Speaking Skills Development*

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INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, English plays a vital role as an international language. Muyassar (2024) describes English as a universal language that facilitates cross-border communication. Proficiency in English is essential for academic, professional, and social interactions, requiring skills such as presenting, negotiating, and engaging in everyday conversations. Strong English-speaking abilities provide access to better educational and career opportunities. Moreover, Miller et al., (2023) assert that effective communication fosters collaboration, critical thinking, and personal growth. As a result, mastering English is a crucial skill in today's interconnected society.

Communication consists of both verbal and non-verbal elements, which are equally important in effective interaction. Verbal communication involves spoken and written language, while non-verbal communication includes body language, gestures, and facial expressions (Holandyah et al., 2024). Combining both forms enhances understanding and helps convey emotions and intentions accurately. Hossain (2024) emphasizes that language is the foundation of all intentional human activity, making communication an essential part of learning. In professional settings, strong communication skills are necessary for leadership, teamwork, and career advancement. Therefore, improving English-speaking skills benefits students in both academic and real-world situations.

To support non-English major students in developing their language skills, Bandar Lampung University has established an English Language Laboratory. One of its key programs is the English for General Communication course, which is mandatory for non-English majors in their third semester. This course focuses on grammar, vocabulary, and practical communication skills for everyday situations, such as class discussions, expressing opinions, and pronouncing words accurately. Through interactive learning methods, students develop their speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills. The

course also introduces cultural and social aspects of English communication, helping students use the language confidently in different contexts.

Understanding students' perceptions of this course is essential in evaluating its effectiveness in improving English-speaking skills. Qiong (2017) defines perception as the interaction between sensory information and cognitive structures, influencing how individuals interpret experiences. Qiong (2017) adds that perception is shaped by personal beliefs, cultural background, and prior experiences. Positive perceptions often lead to higher motivation and better learning outcomes, while negative perceptions may indicate challenges in course delivery or content. By analyzing student feedback, educators can refine teaching methods and enhance learning experiences. Evaluating perceptions also helps address students' difficulties in developing their speaking skills.

The English for General Communication course incorporates role-playing, discussions, and collaborative projects to enhance students' practical language skills. Teachers emphasize commonly used vocabulary and grammar to support effective communication. Engaging in these activities allows students to apply their knowledge in real-world scenarios, improving their confidence in speaking English. Student feedback plays a crucial role in assessing whether the course meets its objectives. Therefore, this study aims to analyze students' perceptions of the English for General Communication course at the English Laboratory of Bandar Lampung University to determine its impact on their English-speaking skills.

METHOD

This study employed a quantitative descriptive method with a survey approach to analyze students' perceptions of the English for General Communication course. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire consisting of 33 closed-ended questions that assess students' comprehension, instructional quality, and speaking skill development. The questionnaire was delivered to 284 students which selected by using random sampling technique. The data collected helps in assessing the effectiveness of the course in improving students' English speaking skill.

Table 1 Categorizing of Students' Perception

Intervals	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
$X > 79$	Very Positive	7	2.5
67 to 78.5	Positive	140	49.3
55.5 to 67	Medium	69	24.3
44 to 55.5	Negative	31	10.9
$X < 44$	Very Negative	37	13.0
Total		284	100

Data analysis follows a quantitative descriptive approach using statistical tools to interpret the findings. Percentages and averages are used to determine trends in students' responses. This analysis helps in understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the course based on student feedback. Ensuring the validity and accuracy of the data is a crucial part of this process. The results provide insights that can contribute to curriculum improvement and teaching strategies. By evaluating students' perceptions, this study aims to determine the effectiveness of the English for General Communication course at the English Language Laboratory, Bandar Lampung University. The findings can help educators refine teaching methods to enhance students' English-speaking abilities. The results will also guide improvements in course structure and content. A better understanding of student experiences allows for a more engaging and effective learning environment. Ultimately, this research contributes to the ongoing development of English language instruction.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

The Influence of Student Perception on Speaking Skills Based on Perception Factors

The English for General Communication course is designed to help non-English major students develop their communication skills in English. The findings indicate that most students perceive the course positively in terms of its impact on their English language skills. Various factors, such as gender, age, experience, motivation, personal perspective, environment, and societal norms, influence these perceptions. Newman et al. (2008) notes that men and women have different communication styles, affecting how they learn and use language. In addition, Krashen (1984) language learning theory suggests that age plays a role in language acquisition, with younger learners generally acquiring languages more easily than older learners.

Students' motivation and beliefs about the effectiveness of different teaching methods also impact their learning process (Munna & Kalam, 2021). A positive attitude toward language learning can enhance engagement and motivation. Additionally, social environments and cultural norms influence students' willingness to use English (Kakita & Palukuri, 2020). A supportive classroom atmosphere with effective teaching strategies can foster motivation and improve learning outcomes. However, some students report dissatisfaction with their learning experiences, citing low motivation, insecurity, and ineffective past learning experiences as barriers to progress. Yusof et al. (2023) highlights that past experiences shape learning attitudes, with negative experiences leading to decreased motivation. According to the Motivation Theory by Bandhu et al. (2024), students with higher confidence in their abilities are more likely to stay motivated and succeed academically. These findings suggest the need for curriculum improvements to address students' concerns and enhance their learning experiences.

The Influence of Student Perception on Speaking Skills Based on Perception Type

The study's results show that most students view the English for General Communication course favorably in terms of its learning methods and resources. Factors such as student engagement, peer interactions, auditory materials, and visual aids play a crucial role in shaping students' learning experiences. According to Gilakjani & Sabouri (2016), listening comprehension is an active process where students analyze auditory input to construct meaning. Engaging and fluency-appropriate listening materials can improve students' comprehension and overall language skills.

Environmental factors also impact learning. A study by Bogerd et al. (2020) found that classroom scents influence students' ability to concentrate and create a comfortable learning environment. Additionally, classroom engagement is a strong predictor of academic success. Students who actively participate in discussions and group activities tend to achieve better learning outcomes (Tutupary et al., 2024). Moreover, social interaction in the classroom fosters problem-solving abilities and deeper comprehension of the material (Albay, 2019). Although most students have a positive perception of the course, some remain neutral or negative due to differences in background, prior experiences, and socioeconomic factors. These findings emphasize the need for interactive learning methods that enhance student engagement and promote positive learning experiences.

The Influence of Student Perception on Speaking Skills Based on Speaking Context

Students generally perceive the English for General Communication course as beneficial for developing their speaking skills. Speaking proficiency is influenced by key factors such as vocabulary, grammar, fluency, comprehension, pronunciation, and self-development. Sunarni (2022) emphasizes that vocabulary is inseparable from other linguistic components like phonology and grammar. Expanding vocabulary enables students to communicate more effectively. Grammar competence also plays a critical role in sentence construction and clarity (Belmekki, 2023).

Fluency, which refers to the ability to speak clearly and effortlessly, requires continuous practice and language exposure (Ho, 2018). Effective communication also depends on comprehension—students must understand their conversation partners to respond appropriately (Mahdi, 2023). Pronunciation impacts clarity; frequent practice helps students improve their articulation. Finally, self-development is crucial for speaking improvement (Alaon et al., 2023). Students must recognize their strengths and weaknesses to enhance their communication skills. These findings suggest that a well-structured curriculum focusing on vocabulary building, grammar reinforcement, and speaking practice can further support students' English proficiency development.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study reveal that students' perceptions significantly impact their ability to develop speaking skills in the English for General Communication course. Most students have a positive perception, recognizing the course as beneficial for improving their English proficiency. Factors such as age, gender, experience, motivation, and social environment influence students' engagement and learning outcomes. Additionally, teaching strategies, classroom atmosphere, and instructional materials play a crucial role in shaping students' learning experiences. While many students find the course helpful, some struggle with motivation, self-confidence, and past negative learning experiences, which hinder their progress. The study highlights the need for interactive teaching methods, auditory and visual learning aids, and peer collaboration to enhance students' communication skills. Addressing these aspects will help create a more effective and engaging learning environment for all students.

Although the course is generally well-received, improvements are necessary to ensure better learning experiences and outcomes for all students. Some students reported dissatisfaction due to ineffective teaching methods, lack of engagement, and difficulty in speaking confidently. Enhancing the curriculum by incorporating student-centered learning approaches, interactive discussions, and real-life communication practice can improve students' speaking proficiency. Teachers should also consider individual learning needs, motivational factors, and confidence-building exercises to support struggling students. Furthermore, clear pronunciation, vocabulary expansion, and fluency practice should be emphasized in the course structure. Future research should explore innovative teaching techniques, curriculum modifications, and additional support mechanisms to optimize student learning. By refining teaching approaches and addressing student concerns, the English for General Communication course can become more effective and impactful for all learners.

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